

Anther culture of Basmati 370 at IRRI. A. Gamma ray-induced green plant regeneration.

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Breeding studies for the improvement of high quality Basmati rice have long been undertaken. So far no variety comparable or superior to Basmati rice has been released.

We conducted experiments on the improvement of the Basmati-type rice through anther culture in the Tissue Culture Facility at IRRI. Gametoclonal variants for plant type and soil constraints can be obtained and consequently fixed when anthers of rice varieties are passed through anther culture. Preliminary studies (Table 1) using different callus induction media showed the predominance of albino plant regeneration. Green plant regeneration was not observed.

To find out if irradiation stress would produce genetic alterations in the cell which would improve callus induction and green plant regeneration, Basmati

Table 1. Anther culture of Basmati 370 in three media.

Media ^a	Callus production (%)	Calli plated (no.)	Albino plant production (no.)
E10	5.71	41	148.78
E10 M	2.56	10	80
E10 T	1.29	6	50

^aE10 consists of Gamborg's B5-basic media with 1 mg 2,4 dichloro-phenoxyacetic acid 2,4-D/liter, 0.5 mg 6-benzylaminopurine (BAP)/liter, 0.5 mg indole-3-acetic acid (IAA)/liter, and 5 mg glucose/liter; E10M consists of E10 with 0.002 M 2 [N-morpholine] ethane sulfonic acid; E10T consists of E10 without 2,4-D, but with 1.5 mg 2,4,5 trichlorophenoxy acetic acid/liter.

Percentage of callus induction and albino plant regeneration as affected by gamma irradiation dosage on Basmati 370.

370 seeds were subjected to irradiation dosages of 15, 20, and 25 krad at an application dose rate of 1.2 krad/min from Cobalt 60 gamma cell. Anthers collected from plants of irradiated seeds in the middle uninucleate to early binucleate stages of pollen development were plated in G4 medium (E10 medium without glucose). Calli produced were transferred to a liquid Murashige and Skoog (MS) regeneration medium with 1 mg kinetin/liter, 1 mg naphthalene acetic acid/liter, and 20 mg abscisic acid (ABA)/liter for 4 wk and then to ABA-free semisolid MS regeneration medium.

Callus production percentage and albino plant regeneration (Fig. 1) were lowest at 20 krad. Green plant regeneration was observed only in 20 krad gamma ray (Table 2). These results show that genetic alterations may have been induced by gamma irradiation which decreased callus production efficiency, but lessened albinism, and triggered green plant regeneration. Although irradiation was directed

Table 2. Effect of irradiation on plant regeneration of Basmati 370 in G4 medium.

Irradiation dosage (krad)	Calli plated (no.)	Calli with green plants (%)
0	10	0
15	61	0
20	23	26.1
25	84	0

randomly to the plant cells, genetic alterations manifested were favorable for green plant regeneration.

We are screening regenerated green plants for agronomic characters and yield. ☞